

Best Banana Processing Practices for Sustainable Banana Supply Chain Management: Thailand Perspective

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Abstract

Banana exports are becoming important sources of Thailand's revenue since bananas are perceived as full of nutrients and people consume them not only as a food staple but also as a nutritious supplement. Since consumers are concerned about the health effects of chemical residue in food, it is becoming important for banana exporters to make sure bananas are not contaminated by chemicals, bacteria, mold or insects. This means improving standards in banana production processes. The receiving and packaging steps begin first, when bananas arrive from the farm. Then bananas are inspected and information is recorded. Next, bananas are weighed, tested, cleaned, cut, and packed. After the final packing data is recorded, labels are put on cartons. Finally, specific storage procedures are required before determining delivery dates for target destinations. Effective banana processing practices will sustain Thailand's competitive edge in the world banana market.

Key words: *Banana, processing, sustainable, supply chain management*

Introduction

Bananas are the world's leading fruit crop. In 2004 about 103 million tons (MT) of bananas were produced worldwide (FAOSTAT, 2004). Very few bananas are processed; they are mostly bought as raw fruit.

Banana exports increased from 14,080 MT in 2004, to 23,733 MT in 2013, and were valued at 8.1 million US dollars (MUSD) and 12.8 MUSD, respectively (UNCOMTRADE, 2014). The main countries for banana exports are China (worth 70% of total world exports), USA (9%), Malaysia (7%) and Japan (6%).

As bananas are becoming one of Thailand's fruit exports, Thailand needs to focus on developing better processing practices to remain competitive in the world market. Chemical residue testing should be done regularly to ensure consumer health and confidence. The most successful banana processing procedures will lead to satisfied consumers.

Customers want processing practices that keep bananas fresh, reduce the perishable rate, and produce an attractive color. If Thailand's banana exports can meet these standards Thailand will maintain a competitive advantage in the world market. Research needs to be conducted to determine the best banana processing practices for Thailand's banana exports.

Literature Review

Tropical fruits and vegetables have become important products in Japan's market as the Japanese are consuming more tropical fruits and vegetables from other countries. However Thai fruit and vegetable exports to Japan are quite low since the competitive market gives Japanese many choices among producers (Kitagawa, 1991). The demand for Thai fruit in Japan

is still high but it must be good quality. If the quality falls below consumer expectations, that producer will never be contacted again.

Banana cutting methods that use mechanical tools cause damage, and make bananas sensitive to weight loss, and invasions of microorganisms. Banana quality will decrease if bananas are damaged in the cutting process (Maria, et al., 2011).

Banana ripening depends mainly on temperature and weight loss, which directly influence banana quality. It is impossible to identify just one banana quality attribute that would explain a loss of banana quality; this means there are many reasons for poor quality bananas (Nunes et al., 2013).

Banana quality deteriorates during the shipping process, since quality is affected by the temperature of the shipping container. High temperatures can be caused by two factors: the air itself and biological processes in banana boxes in containers. Rotting bananas can raise the container temperature for all the other bananas (Jedermann et al. 2013).

Vegetable quality is very important since it reflects to either consumer confidence or market potential. Water loss from vegetables directly affects vegetable's quality and it also limits marketability of fresh vegetables. For example, when chili pepper skins crack, the moisture loss affects their quality. Effective postharvest practices such as setting the right storage temperature can reduce the loss of quality (Jansasithorn et al. 2014).

Banana growers intensified their production systems by increasing technology for farm inputs and their strategies were very labor intensive. An economic analysis noted that higher labor costs increased agricultural subsidies (de Barros et al. 2009).

Increased consumption of fruits and vegetables has created an awareness of health benefits and this is also linked to concerns about illnesses caused by contaminated food. When fruit is only washed with water, contaminants are not reduced as well as when a chlorine treatment is added. Therefore preparing the washing solution, which may include Ph levels, and the washing method become important (Alvarado-Casillas et al. 2007).

Many companies are providing crop protection pesticides, good packing materials, excellent transportation systems, good storage practices and other services, which affect banana quality and production processes. Thai bananas are delicious, have an attractive smell, and are softer than bananas from other countries. However, disadvantages of Thai bananas include thin skins and that they ripen too quickly.

In 2007 Japan allocated an annual import quota of 4 tons of Thai bananas which was expected to increase to 8,000 tons in 2008. Banana exports to Japan outside the quota allocation would receive a higher tariff, at 10 percent or 20 percent, depending on the export season (Pratruangkra, 2011). The banana supply chain can be divided into the following main processes: growing, packing, transportation and receiving, loading at ports, unloading at ports, ripening rate and distribution.

Methodology

The analysis is based on primary data from market surveys both at the manufacturer and farmer levels and by applying the descriptive method to secondary data.

Results

The results are identified below:

1. Cutting Process

Table 1: Banana Cutting Effects

Variables	mean	S.D
1 Bananas are damaged	2.58	1.06
2 Bacterial infections	2.55	0.75
3 Weight loss	2.71	0.98
4 Ripening stimulation	2.97	0.84
Average	2.70	0.90

*Number of respondents=14

Table 1 shows that the average mean effect of banana cutting is 2.70 and the S.D is 0.90. The mean of damaged bananas is 2.58 and S.D is 1.06. The mean of bacterial infections is 2.55 and S.D is 0.75. The mean of weight loss is 2.71 and S.D is 0.98, and the mean of ripening stimulation is 2.97 and S.D is 0.84.

Bacteria can easily infect bananas, particularly when storage conditions and methods are not good. Crop contamination risk depends on many factors such as crop contact with soil. Injured plant parts are also more susceptible to bacterial infection (Bezanson et al. 2014).

This study focuses on current banana processing practices in terms of how they are affecting production processes. The analysis was done after the survey, which considered the best processing practices for banana exports. The exploratory research focused on responses to questionnaires from 14 banana collectors who exported bananas.

The questionnaires were separated into five parts, depending on the research parameter measurements.

The first questionnaires focused on the effects of banana cutting, which can damage the fruit, allow bacterial infections, cause weight loss and stimulate the ripening process. The second questionnaires focused on the effects of banana washing, the overflow stream practice, the removal of unnecessary plant parts, preparations for washing bananas, and the impact of labor intensive processes.

The third questionnaires focused on the effects of drying bananas. For example, allowing bananas to dry naturally in the open air is not suitable, so an air sprayer is recommended. Questions also addressed the removal of unnecessary plant parts and labor-intensive processes.

The fourth questionnaires focused on the effects of these banana packing processes: the preferred vacuum system; the importance of accurate weight measuring, quality control and tracking numbers. The last questionnaires focused on the effects of banana storage. It is important to get the temperature right. Containers must be clean and export cards must be filled out accurately.

Moisture loss directly affects quality and limits a product's marketability. For example, cracked chili pepper skins are susceptible to moisture loss, which affects their quality. Ideal storage practices, such as setting the right storage temperature can have a significant impact on quality improvement (Jansasithorn et al. 2014).

Bananas respond directly to physical damage resulting from mechanical practices. Mechanical practices are responsible for a banana's color, flavor, ripening speed and weight loss. Ideal banana processing therefore must consider best practices for any of the machines used, in order to improve quality (Maia et al. 2011).

Bananas are tropical fruit, so they are sensitive to cold. One study looked at different temperatures over different periods of time. It found that when bananas were kept at 4 C for 1,3 and 5 days first, keep at 20 C later, the result show that the peel turned brown at different rates. Bananas kept for 3 days showed moderate damage and at 5 days showed severe damage. Temperature therefore, has a significant effect on banana quality (Trejo-Marquez & Vendrell 2010).

The best cutting method is to cut the banana carefully by knife, which causes no damage and no curl on the cutting points. After the banana is cut, it can be infected easily by bacteria, so the process after cutting must include sterilization to prevent infection. The knife that was used needs to be sent to the location where sterilization occurs.

2. Washing Process

Table 2 Banana Washing Effects

Variables	mean	S.D
1 Overflow stream practice	3.04	0.93
2 Unneeded plant parts removal	2.79	0.78
3 Preparing water for washing	2.65	0.91
4 Labor intensive process	2.60	0.93
Average	2.77	0.88

*Number of respondents=14

Table 2 shows that the average mean for effects from banana washing, is 2.77 and S.D is 0.88, the mean of over flow stream practice is 3.04 and S.D is 0.93, the mean of unneeded plant part removal is 2.79 and S.D is 0.78, the mean of preparing water for washing is 2.65 and S.D is 0.91, and the mean of labor intensive process is 2.60 and S.D is 0.93.

The washing process uses the overflow stream method, which means bananas are washed in a stream flow in the tank of water and this water will be changed when there is dirt in the tank. In one study fruit was inoculated with bacteria and was then treated by just washing it with water. Then it was treated first, by washing with water and then, by washing with water and adding 200 mg/liter of hypochlorite. The results showed that spraying with a chlorine solution in different concentrations reduced the population of either pathogens, or E.coli, respectively. The water-washing practice did not remove as many pathogens as the combined hypochlorite and water method. This shows that the fruit production process must include a sanitization process at washing and packing facilities (Alvarado-Casilla et al. 2007).

Harvesting orchard crops is very different from modern manufacturing production processes. Managers decide how much fruit will be produced, and when it will be produced. American fruit and vegetable farmers have become increasingly concerned about production costs and labor shortages. Most crops are harvested late, due to a lack of labor, which leads to high production costs and less profit (Calvin & Martin 2010).

Washing methods begin with removing the hull, dirty sap and insects, The sap is washed off after cutting and this process is repeated at least one more time. The water is mixed with soap, and bananas are washed by hand to prevent damage.

3 Drying Process

Table 3 Banana drying effect

Variables	mean	S.D
1 Air-drying method is not suitable	2.97	0.94
2 Air sprayer is recommended	2.95	0.78
3 Unneeded plant parts removed	2.79	0.92
4 Labor intensive process	2.64	0.75
Average	2.83	0.84

*Number of respondents=14

Table 3 shows that the average mean effect of banana drying is 2.83 and S.D is 0.84, and that the air-drying method is not suitable, at 2.97 and S.D is 0.94. The air sprayer is recommended because the mean is 2.95 and S.D is 0.78. The mean of unneeded plant parts removed is 2.79 and S.D is 0.92, and the mean of the labor intensive process is 2.64, and S.D is 0.75.

The air-drying method is not recommended because it will affect the color of the banana skins and freshness. The air sprayer is recommended because air pressure can remove bacteria and dirt particles. Sometimes bananas are not fully clean during the washing process, which allows bacteria and some dirt particles to remain.

Strong air pressure also removes water, small insects and sap. The drying process is similar to other processes that are labor-intensive, since it must be applied by hand.

4 Packing Process

Table 4 Effects of Banana Packing Process

Variables	mean	S.D
1 Vacuum system is preferable	2.95	0.83
2 Weight measuring accuracy needed	2.86	0.79
3 Quality control is important	2.85	0.97
4 Accurate recording of track number	2.79	0.77
Average	2.86	0.84

*Number of respondents=14

Table 4 shows that the average mean of the effects of the banana packing process is 2.86 and S.D is 0.84. The mean of the vacuum system is preferable is 2.95 and S.D is 0.83. The mean of weight measuring accuracy needed, is 2.86 and S.D is 0.79. The mean of quality control is important, is 2.85 and S.D is 0.97. And the mean of accurate recording of track number is 2.79 and S.D is 0.77.

After bananas are cleaned and dried, then the next step is the packing process. This is a critical process that involves applying the track number sticker and quality control.

The packing process begins when the dried bananas are received. The fruit is then weighed for data collection. Alcohol is applied to the cutting points to stop bacteria growth and insects. The trace number stickers are applied to the banana hand for tracking. This process must be carefully done because applying the sticker carelessly could damage the banana hand or end up on the wrong side of a banana hand.

A vacuum system was introduced in this packing process to keep bananas fresh for a longer time, and to prevent damage from insects. This process must be carefully done and evaluated as needed to prevent mold. Mold quickly rots the banana and threatens the quality of the fruit.

One important part of the packing process is weight measuring, which must comply with standard packing weights. For example, packaged golden bananas exported to Japan will be rejected if they weigh more than 11.5 kg.

5 Storage Process

Table 5 Effects of Banana Storage

Variables	mean	S.D
1 Right temperature is needed	3.08	0.97
2 Heat releasing is important	3.00	0.84
3 Containers must be clean	2.94	0.96
4 Export cards must be accurate	2.79	0.85
Average	2.95	0.90

*Number of respondents=14

Table 5 shows that the average mean of effects of banana storage is 2.95 and S.D is 0.90, and the mean of right temperature is needed, is 3.08 and S.D is 0.97. The mean of temperature releasing is important, is 3.00 and S.D is 0.84, the mean of containers must be clean is 2.94 and S.D is 0.96, and finally, the mean of export cards must be accurate is 2.79 and S.D is 0.85.

Bananas risk losing their quality during shipping if the temperature is not right. Temperature management involves air streams and heat that can trigger ripening processes (Jedermann et. al 2013).

The storage process requires temperatures of about 12-14 C. Bananas are stored in containers for 18 hours for temperature adjustment. Heat needs to be released otherwise the bananas will ripen too rapidly. Other banana quality problems occur during shipping when refrigerated containers do not work properly, caused by insufficient cooling conditions (Jedermann et. al 2014).

Export cards from importers are applied to banana boxes so they can be identified by the importers. It is a very important process since it will prevent mistakes at ports, such as the importer receiving the wrong bananas.

Conclusions and Suggestions

There are several components to best practices in banana production processes, and each one has its own characteristics. Banana exports must comply with standard guidelines. For example, the cutting process requires knife sterilization to reduce the risk of bacteria.

The processes required between receiving the harvested bananas and storing them must be carefully followed, as each step involves a critical process to keep quality high, and reduce the risk of bacteria or mold growth.

The best processing practices will delay ripening and create high-quality bananas that are delicious and do not ripen too quickly.

Facility improvement programs are going to be important since some banana producers' facilities do not meet the standards. Facility improvement will directly benefit exporters by increasing their market share, since their banana exports would be of good quality.

Thailand's banana exporters need to create production improvement programs that will help exporters sustain a competitive advantage in the banana export market.

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